

D-JRP12-1.2 Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED

Contributing partners:

BfR, Sciensano, APHA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-JRP12-1.2 Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.
Project Acronym	FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests
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Other contributors	
Due month of the report	M52
Actual submission month	M60
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 15-Dec-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Neither analysis pipeline for the Hi-C data has been published, as follow-up experiments with Hi-C are still ongoing.
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

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1. Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) are mostly disseminated within microbial communities via mobile genetic elements (MGEs). For the analysis of the total DNA from environmental samples with second or third generation sequencing technologies, all cells in the sample are lysed at once prior to DNA extraction. This procedure removes the cellular borders causing chromosomes and extrachromosomal elements like plasmids that residing within the same cell to be separated. Consequently, the species context of ARGs present on plasmids is often not recoverable. ARGs in the chromosomes are often aggregated on genomic islands that are flanked by inverted repeats. This causes problems in a subsequent *de novo* assembly, particularly when a short sequencing technology is used to determine the genomic context of ARGs located on genomic islands.

In the past, a technology known as chromosome conformation capture or 3C as well as its successor Hi-C was used to analyze the 3-dimensional organization of human chromatin to study the interaction between genomic loci that might be distant from each other at the primary structure level (Dekker, Rippe, Dekker, & Kleckner, 2002; Lieberman-Aiden et al., 2009). Thus, insights about functional (e.g. regulatory) roles of genomic regions present at those interacting loci could be obtained such as identifying promoter-enhancers (Ron, Globerson, Moran, & Kaplan, 2017) or studying epigenetic alterations level (Rhie et al., 2019).

The preparation of a Hi-C library (Figure 1) starts with a formaldehyde treatment of the sample to cross-link DNA that is in close proximity within a cell. These links remain intact while the DNA is fragmented with restriction enzymes. During repair of the 5' overhang restriction sites to produce blunt ends, biotinylated residues are incorporated. Subsequently, the cross-linked DNA fragments are ligated in a blunt-end ligation reaction with biotinylated junction sites between fragments that were in close proximity when the cell was intact. Afterwards, the circular DNAs are fragmented and the DNA fragments with biotinylated junctions are selected by pull-down using streptavidin beads. These fragments are then prepared for high-throughput sequencing to generate paired-end reads.

Figure 1: Overview of the Hi-C workflow (Lieberman-Aiden et al., 2009): Cross-linked DNA is fragmented with restriction enzymes. The resulting sticky-ends are repaired to blunt-ends and junctions are marked with biotin. After ligation the DNA-fragments containing incorporated biotin are isolated by pull-down with streptavidin and DNA is prepared for high-throughput sequencing. The prepared Hi-C library is sequenced using a paired-end sequencing technology.

2. Previous studies investigating the applicability of Hi-C

In recent years, Hi-C technology has become more prevalent in the study of microbial communities.

One of the first studies that applied Hi-C in a metagenomics background used an artificial community consisting of five different strains belonging to four species to investigate the recovery of genomes from the community members using Hi-C in combination with simulated metagenome assemblies. Beitel and colleagues observed a within species association of contigs of > 99 % and also that plasmids could be assigned correctly (Beitel et al., 2014).

In another study, similarly, an artificial community consisting of bacteria, archaea and eukaryotes was used to create a shotgun dataset and a Hi-C library (Burton, Liachko, Dunham, & Shendure, 2014). This study also provided an analysis pipeline and reported that it was possible to group most contigs properly to the species they derived from. They also reported difficulties when multiple strains of the same species were present due to a higher signal-noise-ratio caused by the more fragmented metagenomics assembly.

Recently, a few studies showed the feasibility of Hi-C in human fecal samples. In 2020, a study investigated the microbial evolution of the gut microbiome of two individuals over a 10-year period (Yaffe & Relman, 2020). Using Hi-C, they were able to resolve strains, notably 12 persistent strains were characterized through the dynamics of horizontal gene transfer. Another study investigated the gut microbiome of chronically ill patients and showed that Hi-C provided a better reconstruction of several microbial genomes, as well as a better linking of ARGs on genus level and association of prophages to their host genomes (Ivanova et al., 2021).

In a more technical study, a wastewater sample was analyzed using Hi-C (Stalder, Press, Sullivan, Liachko, & Top, 2019). The authors were able to recover the genome of an *Escherichia coli* strain and its constituent plasmid after inoculation at 10^7 CFU/ml and representing an abundance of 10% within the bacterial community present in the sample. Additionally, they could assign single ARGs and several broad and narrow host range plasmids to host families that are known to harbor these respective plasmids. This was also the first study that addressed a possible limit of detection for the Hi-C method. From the results of their analysis, they calculated a minimal host abundance between 0.001% and 0.5%, depending on the considered plasmid/gene and thus, inferred a relative host abundance of 0.01% as the limit of detection. A different group investigated the ability to degrade textile dyes by individual members of a microbiome that was associated with a polluted river in Mexico using Hi-C (Sanchez-Reyes, Breton-Deval, Mangelson, Salinas-Peralta, & Sanchez-Flores, 2022). They were able to link enzymes that might have a role in dye biodegradation to species from the genera *Candidatus*, *Cupriavidus*, *Clostridium* and *Mesorhizobium*.

In addition to studies of human fecal and wastewater samples, several studies in animals have been performed. First, in a very recent study 100 pig fecal microbiomes from conventional and organic farming were investigated regarding the prevalence of antibiotics use (Kalmar et al., 2022). For the analysis they developed their own pipeline, which showed the association of the plasmid-borne lincosamide resistance gene (*Inu(A)*) to three different *Lactobacillus* species only on conventional farms, although these species were also present in samples from organic farms.

Next, in another recent animal study investigating AMR gene transfer in antibiotic-free raised chicken, broiler chicks were challenged with antibiotic-susceptible *Salmonella enterica* serovar Heidelberg (Oladeinde et al., 2021). After 14 days, some of the broiler chicks were found to contain antimicrobial resistant *S. Heidelberg* populations, caused by acquisition of an ARG-carrying plasmid. At ~100 CFU/g cecal sample, Hi-C sequencing was not able to correctly identify the *S. Heidelberg* strain. However, the Hi-C method could identify *Escherichia coli* as the commensal reservoir of the ARG-carrying plasmid, acquired by *S. Heidelberg*. These results suggest that the reduction of antibiotic use on its own is insufficient to limit the transfer of antibiotic resistance from commensal bacteria to *Salmonella enterica*.

Several other animal studies have been performed, but these are of basic science nature, rather than for surveillance or diagnostic purposes. For example, Cuscó and coauthors (2022) used a combination of Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) shotgun libraries and the proximeta Hi-C kit (Phase Genomics) to generate novel Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) from canine fecal samples. Another example is the study of Bickhart et al. (2022), in which fecal samples from sheep were deep-sequenced with Pacific Biosciences Hi-Fi long-read sequencing, in combination with proximeta Hi-C libraries. This study yielded many new MAGs, resolved down to the microbial strain level. Both studies were able to link ARGs and MGEs to their hosts, but required high sequencing coverage (2 MinION flowcells and 75M illumina Hi-C reads for Cusco and coauthors, and more than 200 Gbp of PacBio sequencing data for Bickhart and coauthors), prohibiting an economical use for surveillance or diagnostic purposes.

3. Data analysis and present tools

While there are still only a handful of studies that employ Hi-C on metagenomics samples, several pipelines and tools were published to analyze Hi-C data. All pipelines operate according to the same principle. From the same sample, both a shotgun and a Hi-C library are required and both libraries are sequenced by paired-end short-read sequencing. The shotgun dataset is assembled to provide contigs. Subsequent mapping of the Hi-C reads to these contigs generates contact maps that are then normalized and corrected to remove biases. Utilizing the resulting contact maps, the contigs are binned to metagenome assembled draft genomes using different statistical approaches. These draft genomes can be further analyzed with conventional tools e.g. to detect ARGs or genes that mediate horizontal gene transfer. Multiple strategies to remove biases have been published ten years ago. However, these methods were developed for the analysis of genomes from a single species i.e. usually human, but not for complex communities. This is particularly critical since an assumption of those tools is that all the contigs should have an equal abundance, however this not the case in a metagenomics sample which contains different species at different abundances. Nonetheless, more recently, various tools have been developed for the application of Hi-C in microbiomes.

ProxiMeta is a commercial software that uses the abundance of the contigs for normalization and the Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm to bin the contigs (Press et al., 2017)(Figure 2). By now, some open-source pipelines such as MetaTOR (Baudry, Foutel-Rodier, Thierry, Koszul, & Marbouty, 2019), bin3C (DeMaere & Darling, 2019), HiCBin (Yuxuan Du & Sun, 2022) and HAM-ART (Kalmar et al., 2022) were developed. While some of them are based on relatively simple normalization and correction of Hi-C contacts, one study proposed a more complicated algorithm based on zero-inflated negative binomial regression that accounts for different experimental biases (Y. Du, Laperriere, Fuhrman, & Sun, 2022). From their results the number of restriction sites, contig length and contig coverage are mainly accountable for spurious contacts in Hi-C data. Their normalization method HiCzin was implemented in the open-source pipeline HiCBin (Yuxuan Du & Sun, 2022).

Figure 2: Overview of the commercial ProxiMeta workflow (Phase Genomics) starting with the sample to the analysis with the ProxiMeta platform (from website:

<https://phasegenomics.com/products/proximeta/>)

4. Evaluation of the feasibility of Hi-C to link ARGs and species using an artificial bacterial community

4.1. Methodology

Within WP1 of the FARMED project the feasibility of Hi-C is investigated by the BfR. Therefore, an artificial community (MC, mock community) consisting of 4 different species with a known ARG profile, as well as known genome and plasmid sequences was constructed from single isolates. While most of the species contain mutually exclusive ARGs, some ARGs are also present in two species.

A shotgun library and duplicate Hi-C libraries with two different versions of the commercially available Proximo Hi-C (Microbe) Kit (Phase Genomics Inc, USA) were prepared and paired-end sequenced using the NextSeq 500 system (Illumina, USA). As the recommended sequencing requirement was ~ 100 million read pairs per shotgun library and ~50 million read pairs per Hi-C library, the High-Output Kits by Illumina were used. The resulting data were analyzed with two different pipelines – the commercially available ProxiMeta pipeline and a pipeline developed in the BfR called Hiccap (see 4.2).

Sciensano tested the Proximeta Hi-C kit (Phase Genomics Inc, USA) on a defined mock community developed by BfR. The obtained Hi-C library was sequenced on Illumina MiSeq, which resulted in a total of 18 million read pairs. Additionally, an Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) shotgun library using the ONT rapid kit (SQK-RAD004) was made from the mock community and was subsequently sequenced on a MinION R9.4.1 flowcell, generating 24 Gbp of sequencing data. The combined Hi-C and ONT data were analyzed through both the ProxiMeta pipeline as well as a custom workflow (section 4.3).

4.2. Workflow of the mapping-based pipeline Hiccap

The BfR implemented a snakemake pipeline called Hiccap for the analysis of Hi-C data.

4.3. Workflow of assembly and binning based Sciensano pipeline for combined analysis of ONT shotgun and ProxiMeta Hi-C data

Sciensano developed a workflow to analyze Hi-C reads in combination with ONT shotgun data.

4.4. Results

The effect of different parameters (different mappers and species databases) on the analysis of Hi-C datasets using Hiccap was tested and compared to the results from the commercial ProxiMeta pipeline by ProxiMeta using the mock community of 4 species. For mapping with Hiccap, two different mappers STAR (Hiccap-STAR) and minimap2 (Hiccap-minimap2) were used. Additionally, 3 different databases were tested: (i) a species database containing the complete chromosomes of the 4 MC isolates (MC isolates), (ii) a species database containing one complete genome for each of the 4 MC species derived from the Kalamari database (<https://github.com/liskatz/Kalamari>) (MC species single), and lastly, (iii) a species database containing one or more representative and reference genomes from the NCBI RefSeq database for each of the 4 MC species. In order to evaluate the results, the specificity, sensitivity and accuracy were calculated and the expected ARG-to-species associations were compared to the obtained associations. Alternatively, the results were filtered by different calculated/statistical variables derived from the incidence of Hi-C links compared to the species genome and ARG coverage.

The results from the study showed that both the Hiccap and the ProxiMeta pipelines were able to correctly assign most of the ARGs to species with a specificity >0.85. The highest specificity was obtained when using the MC isolates database in combination with the STAR mapper. Filtering improved the specificity, in particular for the results generated with minimap2, but it also reduced the sensitivity. This was mainly observed in the STAR mapping results, but had only a minor effect for the minimap2 results. Therefore, different thresholds must be determined for the two different mapping strategies. Despite the different requirements for filtering, a sensitivity of >0.75 could be achieved with both mappers and all three databases.

An accuracy of ARG-to-species associations of >0.83 was obtained for the analysis of the Hi-C datasets with the three different databases and two pipelines. In general, we observed the highest accuracy when the database containing the isolate genomes (MC isolates) was used and that filtering of the results improved the accuracy of the results. Filtering improved the results generated with the Hiccap-minimap2 pipeline, but not with the Hiccap-STAR pipeline. Lastly, ARGs that were present in more than one species could be correctly assigned to the two different species (data not shown).

Sciensano performed a preliminary comparison of the ProxiMeta pipeline and the custom workflow. In both cases, the ONT-generated assembly was less fragmented compared to the previously available isolate Illumina WGS data. In the case of *E. coli*, the chromosome was split into two contigs in the available reference sequence, whereas ONT data generated a complete circular contig. In both the ProxiMeta and the custom workflows, most plasmid contigs were attributed to their corresponding host species through binning methods.

4.5. Conclusion

The conducted study showed that an assignment of ARGs to species is possible by using Hi-C with an accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity of $>90\%$. Here, we observed slightly better results when the BfR - developed mapping-based pipeline Hiccap was used compared to the commercial assembly-based ProxiMeta pipeline. However, the specificity was dependent on the database and better results were obtained with close mapping references. Therefore, these results show that there is a possible future solution to solving the deconvolution of metagenomic samples including plasmid and ARG attribution without the need for a shotgun dataset, which represents a substantial cost factor.

Sciensano showed that Hi-C sequencing can be performed with lower sequencing throughput than conventional Hi-C studies, possibly reducing to some extent the cost for such analyses. A similar result was found by Kent et al. (2020), who performed a rarefaction analysis and demonstrated that most unique gene-taxa associations were found with 15M Hi-C read pairs. Taken together with the results obtained by BfR, this suggests that Hi-C information can be valuable with no or only a limited throughput shotgun library. However, more detailed studies are required to determine the costs and feasibility in more complex samples.

5. Limitations of the method

Hi-C can overcome a major drawback of metagenomics, namely the separation of plasmids and their hosts. Thus, it allows for the study of horizontal gene transfer mediated by plasmids within bacterial communities (Yaffe & Relman, 2020). This was previously only possible via two methods — single-cell sequencing and microbiological sampling, followed by whole-genome sequencing. While single-cell sequencing is highly susceptible to contamination (Blainey, 2013; Woyke et al., 2011), the experimental capacity and culturability of bacteria limits the significance of the latter method. Therefore, the proof-of-concept of Hi-C sequencing within the context of the FARMED project has been delivered, i.e. using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.

Analysis of Hi-C data from metagenome samples is still a very new field and only a handful of open-source tools have been released in the last 3 years. As a result, the analysis of Hi-C data is not yet standardized and far away from routine. Correction methods to detect spurious links are still under development. It is particularly difficult to detect spurious links between plasmids and contigs derived from closely related strains (Stalder et al., 2019). Moreover, the study of low abundant strains remains a major challenge and few bacteria of a strain or single events of plasmid transfer might not be traceable due to insufficient sampling, which is however a general problem in the metagenomics field. Despite the advantages offered by Hi-C and limitations that might be overcome or accepted in the near future, one of the major limits is the involved costs per sample and making the method unaffordable for the broader scientific community, let alone routine monitoring settings. Additionally, Hi-C is not yet accessible for

field studies since the laboratory procedure is time consuming, temperature dependent and requires a variety of laboratory equipment, reagents and trained personnel (van Berkum et al., 2010).

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This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Zankari, E., Hasman, H., Cosentino, S., Vestergaard, M., Rasmussen, S., Lund, O., Aarestrup, F. M., & Larsen, M. V. (2012). Identification of acquired antimicrobial resistance genes. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 67(11), 2640–2644. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dks261>